

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**WORLDWIDE PREVALENCE OF HELICOBACTER PYLORI
INFECTION: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW STUDY**¹Dr Nurmeen Amber, ²Dr Samira Ashraf, ³Dr Kanza Yousaf, ⁴Dr Abdul Raheem.¹MBBS, Sharif Medical and Dental College, Lahore., ²MBBS, Sharif Medical and Dental College, Lahore., ³MBBS, King Edward Medical University, Lahore., ⁴MBBS, Central Park Teaching Hospital, Lahore.

Article Received: April 2019

Accepted: May 2019

Published: June 2019

Abstract:

Objective: The epidemiology of *Helicobacter pylori* infection has changed with improvements in sanitation and methods of eradication. We performed a systematic review to evaluate changes in the global prevalence of *H. pylori* infection.

Method: systematic search of the MEDLINE and EMBASE databases for studies of the prevalence of *H. pylori* infection was done we analyzed data based on United Nations geoscheme regions and individual countries. We used a random effects model to calculate pooled prevalence estimates with 95% confidence intervals (CIs), weighted by study size. We extrapolated 2015 prevalence estimates to obtain the estimated number of individuals with *pylori* infection

Results: Among 14,006 reports screened, we identified 263 full-text articles on the prevalence of *H. pylori* infection; 184 were included in the final analysis, comprising data from 62 countries. Africa had the highest pooled prevalence of *H. pylori* infection (70.1%; 95% CI, 62.677.7), whereas Oceania had the lowest prevalence (24.4%; 95% CI, 18.530.4). Among individual countries, the prevalence of *H. pylori* infection varied from as low as 18.9% in Switzerland (95% CI, 13.124.7) to 87.7% in Nigeria (95% CI, 83.192.2). Based on regional prevalence estimates, there were approximately 4.4 billion individuals with *pylori* infection worldwide in 2015.

Conclusion: In a systematic to assess the prevalence of *H. Pylori* infection worldwide, we observed large amounts of variation among regions—more than half the world's population is infected. These data can be used in development of customized strategies for the global eradication.

Key words: Gastric Cancer, *Helicobacter Pylori* Infection, Prevalence

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Please cite this article in press Nurmeen Amber et al., *Worldwide Prevalence Of Helicobacter Pylori Infection: A Systematic Review Study.*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci.*, 2019; 06(06).

INTRODUCTION:

A continued reduction in gastric cancer incidence and mortality has been observed worldwide for several decades, though the trends differ between [1-3] and within countries [4-8]. The improvement in the living standards of people decreases in gastric cancer rates [9]. The recognition of *Helicobacter pylori* as a human carcinogen [10-11] Yet the prevalence of this bacterium is still present, especially in the Far East. The main reason of chronic gastritis and the principal etiological agent for gastric cancer and peptic ulcer disease is the *Helicobacter pylori* fig 1. In most regions, the main mechanism of spread is interfamilial transmission. The prevalence remains high in most developing countries and is generally related to socioeconomic status and levels of hygiene.

It is estimated that *H. pylori* infection affects more than half of the adult population worldwide [12] and is responsible for 75 % of all gastric cancer cases [13]. The systematic assessment of large population-based surveys addressing the prevalence of infection may provide robust evidence for understanding the trends in the exposure to this major risk factor across

settings with distinct patterns of variation in gastric cancer mortality.

Global and regional HP prevalence has not been systematically reported until now. Recent interest has focused on HP eradication as strategy of eliminating gastric cancer. However, the epidemiology and clinical manifestations of the infection has been changing, especially in developed countries. For example, gastric cancer and peptic ulcer incidence has continued to fall in Western Europe, the United States, and Japan. Global eradication strategies require up-to-date information regarding HP prevalence and disease burden.

We performed a systematic review of population-based studies reporting HP prevalence of different countries over different time periods, with the premise that these data would provide crucial updates about HP global disease burden and the information to plan appropriate strategies for allocating health care resources. Understanding the global epidemiologic patterns of HP will aid us in prioritizing and customizing public health efforts to better manage the burden of this disease.

Fig 1: *Helicobacter pylori* infections

METHOD:**Literature Search and Study Selection**

This systematic review was performed in accordance to the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) 2009 guidelines. A search using keywords from a combination of Medical Subject Headings and free text including terms related to HP and prevalence was performed in MEDLINE and EMBASE via Ovid. All suitable published papers from 1960 to 2018 were identified. The search strategy is described in the Supplementary Table 1.

Comprehensive inclusion and exclusion criteria were pre-defined (Table 1) to facilitate objective screening of papers. Only published original observational reports on the prevalence of HP in study populations that were reflective of the general population at national or sub-national levels were included. Systematic reviews, meta-analyses, conference presentations, and letters or correspondences were excluded.

Table 1. Study Selection Criteria

Criteria
<p>Selection, grading, and clarification of studies</p> <p>HP diagnosis must be confirmed by one of the following tests: HP serology, HP stool antigen, urea breath test, biopsies for Campylobacter-like organism test, rapid urease test, histology, or culture</p> <p>The study participants must be reflective of the general population in the region</p> <p>Data from multicenter and multinational studies were extracted separately and sorted by countries and regions</p> <p>Studies were classified as national (if stated in the report or multicenter study involving multiple regions in the country), sub-national (if only a particular region was evaluated), and city level</p> <p>Clarifications with the corresponding authors of studies with missing data were made if possible (eg, without specified HP diagnostic method or study period)</p> <p>Attempts were made to rectify any data errors found in the studies, in consultation with the corresponding authors whenever possible</p> <p>Exclusion criteria</p> <p>Publication type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guidelines Perspectives, correspondence, letters Conference abstract or presentation without formal publication Systematic reviews or meta-analyses Surveillance registration or national notifiable disease reports of HP Studies without defined study periods <p>Study type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Economic analyses Modeling, time series, or transmission studies; mortality or survival analyses; diagnostic assay or test performance studies; animal studies <p>Study Population</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Study populations that are typically associated with higher prevalence of HP (eg, patients with gastric cancer, peptic ulcers) High-risk population groups (migrants, refugees, prisoners, individuals [groups] classified as low socioeconomic status, homeless people, adoptees) Study participants that were restricted to selected age groups (eg, children, elderly) <p>Testing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> HP diagnosis made from methods other than the 4 conventional tests stated above Studies not reporting the method of HP diagnosis Self-reported HP infection Studies not reporting the number of individuals on which the prevalence estimate was based

Data Extraction and Quality Appraisal:

Full-text review was performed for all the selected papers and data extracted and sorted by the following variables: name of study, leading author, journal, publication year, study period, type of study, study location (country and sub-national region), HP diagnostic methods used, participant details (number,

age, sex ratio), total number of participants, number of HP positive participants, and HP crude prevalence rate.

Data on prevalence as a percent of the number of HP-positive participants relative to total number tested were recorded or calculated with 95% confidence

intervals (CIs). The quality of the remaining papers was rated with the Cochrane Collaboration endorsed Newcastle-Ottawa Quality Assessment Scale,

10 which was designed to assess aspects of population-based studies of prevalence.

Table 2.: Helicobacter pylori Prevalence and Number of People Living with H pylori in the General Population within Each Country Grouped by United Nations Regions

Variable	No. of reporting studies	No. of participants	Prevalence estimates, % (95% CI)	Population size per country ^a	HP-positive population
UN African region					
Benin	1	446	74.1	10,880,000	8,056,640
Burkina Faso	1	188	(70.078.1)	18,106,000	8,475,419
Democratic Republic of Congo	1	133	46.8	77,267,000	59,835,565
Egypt	1	200	(39.753.9)	91,508,000	37,435,923
Libya	1	360	77.4	6,278,000	4,795,764
Nigeria	2	648	(70.384.6)	182,202,000	159,700,053
South Africa	2	1539	40.9	54,490,000	42,306,036
Tunisia	2	348	(15.466.4)	11,254,000	8,191,787
UN Latin American and Caribbean region					
			76.4		
			(72.080.8)		
			87.7		
			(83.192.2)		
			77.6		
			(59.895.5)		
			72.8		
			(53.791.9)		
Argentina	1	493	49.1	43,417,000	21,313,405
Bahamas	1	204	(44.753.5)	388,000	224,419
Brazil	6	2937	57.8	207,848,000	147,946,206
Chile	1	2615	(51.164.6)	17,948,000	13,383,824
Ecuador	1	90	71.2	16,144,000	11,659,197
Guadeloupe ^b	1	854	(66.076.4)	468,000	229,367
Mexico	2	11,820	74.6	127,017,000	66,709,328
Panama	1	74	(72.976.2)	3,929,000	2,123,625
UN Northern American region					
			72.2		
			(63.081.5)		
			49.0		
			(35.362.8)		
			52.5		
			(24.780.3)		
			54.1		
			(42.765.4)		
Canada	1	316	38.0	35,940,000	13,646,418
Greenland	2	756	(32.643.3)	56,000	23,178
United States ^c	8	16,235	41.4	321,774,000	114,455,012
UN Asian region					
			(37.944.9)		
			35.6		
			(30.041.1)		

Central Asia (n ¼ 1)			79.5		
Kazakhstan			(74.984.2)		
Eastern Asia (n ¼ 47)					
China			55.8		
Japan			(51.859.9)		
Korea			51.7		
Taiwan			(44.758.7)		
Southern Asia (n ¼ 13)			54.0		
Iran	1	288	(50.157.8)	17,625,000	14,013,638
India	22	103,128	53.9		
Lebanon	11	48,979	(36.671.2)	1,376,049,000	768,110,552
Nepal	11	121,493	59.0	126,573,000	65,387,612
Pakistan	3	10,616	(51.566.5)	25,155,000	13,571,123
South-Eastern Asia (n ¼ 8)			63.5	23,381,000	12,600,021
Malaysia	8	5256	(53.473.5)	79,109,000	46,658,488
Singapore	2	407	52.0	1,311,051,000	831,861,860
Thailand	1	308	(46.447.5)	5,851,000	3,039,595
Vietnam	1	383	70.1	28,514,000	19,974,057
Western Asia (n ¼ 8)	1	205	(65.975.1)	188,925,000	152,991,465
Israel			81.0		
Oman	3	9168	(75.686.4)	30,331,000	8,677,699
Saudi Arabia	2	953	28.6	5,604,000	2,287,553
Turkey	1	179	(19.038.2)	67,959,000	29,616,532
UN European region	2	1241	40.8	93,448,000	65,712,634
			(37.743.9)		
	2	688	43.6	8,064,000	5,555,290
	2	499	(36.350.8)	4,491,000	2,205,081
	1	364	70.3	31,540,000	20,794,322
	3	6036	(63.377.4)	78,666,000	60,761,618
			68.9		
			(62.775.1)		
			49.1		
			(11.586.7)		
			65.9		
			(61.170.8)		
			77.2		
			(71.483.1)		
Eastern Europe (n ¼ 10)	3	4644	41.2	10,543,000	4,342,662
Czech Republic	3	7806	(24.857.6)	38,612,000	25,707,870
Poland	1	960	66.6	19,511,000	13,372,839
Romania	3	4771	(56.476.7)	143,457,000	112,585,054
Russian Federation			68.5		
Northern Europe (n ¼ 22)	2	37,741	(65.671.5)	5,669,000	1,254,550
Denmark	2	2198	78.5	1,313,000	1,083,356
Estonia	1	896	(67.189.9)	5,503,000	3,124,603
Finland	2	834	22.1	329,000	118,341
Iceland	1	1000	(17.826.5)	4,688,000	2,015,840
Ireland			82.5		
			(75.190.0)		
			56.8		

Variable	No. of reporting studies	No. of participants	Prevalence estimates, % (95% CI)	Population size per country ^a	HP-positive population
			(46.567.0)		
			36.0		
			(32.739.2)		
			43.0		
			(39.946.1)		
Latvia	1	3564	79.2 (77.980.5)	1,971,000	1,561,229
Norway	3	4068	30.7 (20.540.8)	5,211,000	1,597,172
Sweden	5	7149	26.2 (18.334.1)	9,779,000	2,563,076
United Kingdom	5	15,098	35.5 (14.556.5)	64,716,000	22,974,180
Southern Europe (n ¼ 22)					
Albania	1	101	53.5 (43.763.2)	2,897,000	1,549,026
Croatia	3	6538	52.7 (42.562.8)	4,240,000	2,234,056
Greece	3	1571	52.1 (40.264.0)	10,955,000	5,708,651
Italy	5	9055	56.2 (46.965.4)	59,798,000	33,606,476
Portugal	1	2067	86.4 (84.987.9)	10,350,000	8,942,400
San Marino	2	3765	47.5 (40.554.5)	32,000	15,200
Spain	7	2721	54.9 (48.661.1)	46,122,000	25,307,141
Western Europe (n ¼ 16)					
Belgium	3	27,845	32.7 (22.443.0)	11,299,000	3,694,773
France ^d	1	64	46.9 (34.759.1)	64,395,000	30,188,376
Germany	8	19,015	35.3 (31.239.4)	80,689,000	28,483,217
Netherlands	3	8592	35.5 (30.141.0)	16,925,000	6,011,760
Switzerland	1	175	18.9 (13.124.7)	8,299,000	1,565,191
UN Oceania region					
Australia ^c	4	4485	24.6 (17.232.1)	23,969,000	5,905,962
New Zealand	1	1060	24.0 (21.426.5)	4,529,000	1,085,148

RESULT:

A total of 14,006 records were identified from both databases, of which 6188 records were duplicates, 7611 records were excluded based on selection criteria, 22 records were removed due to inaccessible full text, and 3 records could not be translated for review (Figure 2). Two records were found in hand searches, and a total of 184 papers were included after full-text review (11 from Africa, 75 from Asia, 66 from Europe, 13 from Latin America and Caribbean, 13 from Northern America, and 6 from Oceania), reporting HP prevalence in 62 countries with 257,768 (48.5%) participants tested HP-positive, out of a total of 531,880 participants. The countries with the highest number of reports were China

(n¼21), Korea (n¼12), Japan (n¼11), United States (n¼10), Germany (n¼8), and Iran (n¼8).

A summary of the distribution of papers by regions is shown in Supplementary Table. Prevalence of HP in the indigenous population of the United States and Australia was higher than the general population. In Australia, the pooled HP prevalence estimate for the general population was 24.6% (95% CI, 17.2%–32.1%), but was as high as 76.0% (95% CI, 72.3%–79.6%) in the rural Western Australian indigenous community. In the United States, the pooled HP prevalence estimate for the general population was 35.6% (95% CI, 30.0%–41.1%), but it was 74.8% (95% CI, 72.9%–76.7%) in the Alaskan indigenous population.

Table 3. Helicobacter pylori Prevalence and Number of People Living With H pylori in the General

Variable	Prevalence estimates, %, 95% CI)	Population size per region/country ^a	HP-positive population (range)
UN Africa region	79.1 (62.695.6)	1,186,178,282	938,267,021 (742,547,6041,133,986,437)
UN Latin American and Caribbean region	63.4 (59.267.6)	634,386,567	402,201,083 (375,556,847428,845,319)
Caribbean	52.6 (45.260.0)	43,199,297	22,731,470 (19,526,08225,919,578)
Central America	53.0 (32.673.5)	172,740,074	91,621,335
South America	69.4 (63.974.9)	418,447,196	(56,313,264126,963,954)
UN Northern American region	37.1 (32.341.9)	357,838,036	290,318,665 (267,387,758313,416,949)
UN Asian region	54.7 (51.358.1)	4,393,296,014	132,614,776 (115,581,685149,934,137)
Central Asia	79.5 (74.984.2)	67,314,033	2,403,132,920
Eastern Asia	54.1 (50.857.5)	1,612,286,941	(2,253,760,8552,552,504,984)
Southern Asia	61.6 (55.967.4)	1,822,974,074	53,521,388 (50,418,21056,678,415)
South–Eastern Asia	43.1 (31.554.8)	633,489,946	872,892,150
Western Asia	66.6 (56.177.0)	257,231,020	(819,041,766927,064,991)
UN European region	47.0 (41.852.1)	738,442,070	1,123,134,327 (1,019,042,5071,228,684,525)
Eastern Europe	62.8 (48.377.2)	292,942,778	273,287,563
Northern Europe	41.6 (32.450.7)	102,357,768	(199,549,332347,152,490)
Southern Europe	55.0 (49.161.0)	152,347,892	171,212,967
Western Europe	34.3 (31.337.2)	190,793,632	(144,306,602198,067,885)
UN Oceania region	24.4 (18.530.4)	39,331,130	347,067,773 (308,668,785384,728,318)
Global	—	—	183,850,887 (141,491,361226,151,824) 42,550,124 (33,163,91651,895,388) 83,852,280 (74,802,81492,932,214) 66,396,184 (59,718,40670,975,231) 9,608,595 (7,276,25911,956,663) 4,356,096,968 (3,750,167,5664,961,780,681)

Population in the United Nations Regions

a Based on United Nations 2015 Revision of World Population Prospects total population estimates.

Fig 2: Flowchart of study selection

DISCUSSION:

HP infection continues to be a major public health issue worldwide. This global systematic review shows that in 2015, approximately 4.4 billion individuals worldwide were estimated to be positive

for HP. This is the most comprehensive and up-to-date systematic review of the worldwide prevalence of HP. Wide variation in the prevalence of HP between regions and countries had confirmed by this review study. Prevalence is highest in Africa

(79.1%), Latin America and the Caribbean (63.4%), and Asia (54.7%). In contrast, HP prevalence is lowest in Northern America (37.1%) and Oceania (24.4%). At the turn of the 21st century, the prevalence of HP has been declining in highly industrialized countries of the Western world, whereas prevalence has plateaued at a high level in developing and newly industrialized countries. The widening differential gap in prevalence has important implications on the future worldwide prevalence of sequelae associated with HP, including peptic ulcer

disease and gastric cancer. These differences in HP prevalence likely reflect the level of urbanization, sanitation, access to clean water, and varied socioeconomic status. There are significant differences in the HP prevalence even within the same country. Different racial groups in the United States have different HP prevalence. It was reported that the prevalence in non-Hispanic whites ranges from 18.4% to 26.2% and that in non-whites ranges from 34.5% to 61.6%. Prevalence can be as high as 75.0% in the Alaskan Native population.

Fig 3: Global prevalence of HP choropleth map. Certain regions are magnified to better display the smaller countries. The online interactive global map showing the HP prevalence can be found at the following URL: <https://people.ucalgary.ca/wgkaplan/HP2016.html>.

CONCLUSION:

This review provides a comprehensive overview of the prevalence of HP. Variation in prevalence of HP

observed in different geographic areas and across time suggests that prevalence is influenced by living conditions, such as hygiene status and

industrialization of society.

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